

Dialectical Units of Language and Thought

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ABSTRACT: The role of the mother tongue in the spiritual development of man, in the cultural and enlightenment development of society is extremely important. Language is the most objective and indestructible mirror of national spirituality, enlightenment and culture. It is said in a hadith: “The beauty of a man is in his tongue”. This article discusses the integral aspects of language, word formation, language and thinking.

KEYWORDS: Spirituality, Enlightenment And Culture, Dialectical, Language, Covenant, Vocabularies.

INTRODUCTION

The role of the mother tongue in the spiritual development of man, in the cultural and enlightenment development of society is extremely important. Language is the most objective and indestructible mirror of national spirituality, enlightenment and culture. It is said in a hadith: “The beauty of a man is in his tongue”. From time immemorial, every nation, every people has had great respect for its language. There is an inexhaustible pleasure of melting in the mouth of the magic tones of this language. It is comforting not to find a symbol in the language. It stands now not to give this rare wealth to the worlds. Because language is the cornerstone of the unity of the nation, if it is lost, the nation will be lost. “All the virtues permeate the human heart, first of all, with the mother goddess; the unique charm of the mother tongue ... The mother tongue is the soul of the nation. Any nation that loses its language will inevitably lose its identity”. Hence, the main symbol of the existence and unity of a nation is language.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Perfect spirituality and enlightenment are the decisive factors in ensuring the struggle of our national idea, the main goal of which is the development of the Motherland, the peace of the country, the well-being of the people. That is why the education of "love for the mother tongue, which is the immortal soul of the nation" plays an important role in the promotion of the national idea. There is a proverb in the book "Devonulug'otitürk" by our ancestor Mahmud Kashgari, who made a gold box for the Turkish vocabulary. The great scholar Yusuf Khas Hajib's epic Qutadg'ubilig contains a number of beautiful sayings about the "language ardami" (language etiquette): "When he speaks knowingly, the word is wisdom, and the word of the foolish eats his own head". "The covenant is the word of splendor, and the tongue is the word of splendor. "He who is born will die, he will be blind, he will die without a name, Speak your word kindly, and you will not die forever".

It has been known since ancient times that language is a social phenomenon; it arose out of the need for interaction between people. Naturally, the first and foremost function of language is to be a means of communication between people. The ancient Greek sage Aristotle, in his book Rhetoric, states that the main virtue of speech is that it is definite, that "if speech is not clear, it cannot achieve its purpose". It is also true that the purpose of speech, that is, the speech that is constructed to express it, can never be clear unless the idea itself is clear and distinct. In order for a speech to be clear, the speaker must first be able to clarify what he is trying to say. Often researchers quote the Great Russian writer LN Tolstoy as saying, “Uncertainty in words is undoubtedly a sign of uncertainty of thought”.

They quote. The 16th-century French philosopher Michel Montaigne also has a great deal to say: “I think, based on Socrates’ conclusions, that a person who has a living and clear idea of something in his mind can express it in any language, albeit in an incomprehensible dialect”. Of course, it is necessary to think about things in order to form clear ideas in the mind. Not being able to name things accurately and clearly is, of course, a consequence of not knowing them well. The inability to think or the laziness of thinking does not allow for clear speech. After all, much has been said about the dialectical unity of language and thought, there is no language without thought, no language without thought, all our knowledge is formed, formed and developed according to language and thought. The correct and clear expression of real reality, objects and phenomena in nature and society in speech is the main essence of concrete speech. Therefore, the communicative quality of clarity is determined because of the balance between SPEECH and reality. This implies the correct use of the Word, which is the basic unit of speech. Hence, the

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accuracy of it is a communicative quality that arises because of the fact that the word is used in full accordance with the meaning of the language; the word is strictly consistent with the thing-event it expresses in reality. Knowledge of the reality described, a good understanding of the system of meanings in the language, a careful look at the content of speech are crucial in the formation of specific speech skills. Then you can taste the exact word that is most appropriate and unmistakable for the expression. The following passage from AskadMukhtor's poem "Words" emphasizes the importance of the word's place in speech:

"Sometimes the words shout 'Bejoman', Sometimes they are like a horse on a hunt. Sometimes they are indifferent to everything, they do not care, and they do not tremble. Choose him, if he strikes you, be jealous of the editor.

It is known that in man the understanding of identity, the expression of national consciousness and thinking, the spiritual connection between generations is manifested through language. Spiritual renewal in our society thanks to national independence, radical attention to the education system, the introduction of innovative technologies in all areas of continuing education, as well as the inculcation of spiritual and moral traditions, humanism and democratic values in the minds of the younger generation. Bringing up the next generation morally, ideologically, politically, comprehensively mature and cultured has always been the main goal of the state and society. Only a physically and spiritually mature person can sincerely serve the development of society, the development of the country. In the development and progress of our society, it is important to say that the role of our future successors, who are the foundation of our future, present and future, is invaluable. Language and thinking are inextricably linked, and thinking emerges through words. Contemplation is the conceptual expression of the outside world. The word reflects the conditional name of the concept. In the process of studying the materials, students become acquainted with important sources about the enrichment of our language with new words, word formation. The teacher relies on the children's life experience, speech practice, both in teaching theoretical knowledge and in applying the given knowledge in practice. No matter how rich the vocabulary of a language, without grammar it is dead. The lexical composition of a language does not perform a communicative function on its own. To serve the purpose of communication, the words in the vocabulary are grammatically interconnected with each other to form a sentence. It is through this structured sentence that thought is expressed. The nature of each aspect of a language is reflected in the specificity of the language units within it. A word is the basic unit of meaning of a language. Words and phrases express specific objects, abstract concepts, emotions. The development of scientific thinking became the basis for the creation of new methods in linguistics, the drawing of new theoretical conclusions, and linguistics began to develop gradually. New views on language led to new directions, new perspectives to the formation of new sections of language. In general, great work has been done in linguistics on the study of the lexical structure of all languages in groups on the basis of subjects represented by lexemes, a great deal of experience has been accumulated. In this regard, scientific works and dictionaries have been created, which contain the invaluable wealth and treasures of the peoples. The main difference of a lexeme-word from other similar signs is that it is inextricably linked with the object it represents. At the same time, it directly reflects the real being in accordance with the concepts that embody the generalized features of a particular group of objects. The lexical-semantic features of a word combine its lexical, grammatical and semantic aspects. Because words not only form the vocabulary of a language in this way, they generally require all the connections in the system and structure of the language. The lexical meaning of a word and the nature of its application are known in a phrase or sentence. Morphological analysis according to word structure is an important tool in helping students understand its lexical meaning and spelling morphemes correctly. It is well known that no general definition of a word has been created in linguistics. The word cannot have several "meanings", - writes VA Zvegintsev. "Literally, a generalization is strengthened by a certain generalization, and unless this generalization process stops throughout the life and development of the language, a generalization in several directions in a single word cannot take place in parallel". Therefore, the word does not have more than one meaning. A word is the most meaningful unit of language and has the property of being freely recreated in speech when composing a sentence. The word is the most important unit of language because all the basic elements of the language structure are united in the word. The following conclusions can be drawn from the comments made about the word. A word is a phonetic and grammatically formed, complete unit of language that has independence, expresses certain meanings or emotions. Thus, the word has integrity, specificity in terms of meaning and formation, it is a semantic and phonetic, grammatical integrity. and learns the laws of development. This is because the thinking that is always expressed in language reflects the features that are inherent in objects and things, which occur in their interrelationships and relationships. Navoi, who clearly noticed this feature of thinking in his time:

He said: Man, who does everything,

He is a man who knows by thinking.

The idea of solving celestial problems

It was his attention that made the sky difficult,— say writes.

CONCLUSION

In short, a word is a unit with an independent meaning. However, this view does not apply to all languages. In Uzbek, Russian, English, German, French, Spanish and many other languages, the word is an independent unit. A word is a unit of form (sound form) and content, a unit that combines semantic and grammatical integrity. It is scientifically studied in four stages, both formally

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and semantically in the structure of language: - phonologically, the phoneme structure of a word and its accent (accent) structure are studied; - morphologically the morphemic structure of the word is scientifically analyzed; - lexically, the fact that the word is a unit of terminology, that is, the aspect related to naming is considered; - semantically different aspects of the meaning of the word are studied. Lexical meaning is expressed through the material part of a word (the material part of a word is the main, lexical part), so lexical meaning is sometimes referred to as material meaning. The grammatical meaning of a word is its formal part (the formal part of a word is the rest of the main part, the core), so it is also called the formal meaning of the word. Lexical meaning - the meaning of the main part of a word - is studied in lexicology, while grammatical meaning - the meaning of the formal part of a word - is studied in grammar. While the lexical meaning of a word is expressed through a stem, the grammatical meaning is often expressed through an affix. This phenomenon is a form formed from the expression of grammatical meaning by such means - a grammatical form. A grammatical form is a grammatical meaning expressed by means of the specified type: there is no grammatical meaning without a grammatical form. There are many similarities in language. All of these analogies have relativity. In fact, language cannot be compared to anything in the world. A complex system of relationships has infinite possibilities, vast resources, and arises only through the process of communication between people. According to the American scientist U. Whitney, "language is not a simple aggregate of parts of the same type. It is a complex system of elements that are closely interconnected, one complementing the other. This system is integral and has a symmetrical structure. The nature of language is based on the practical activity of the mind, which is able to contain the information in the world outside and inside, and then to use each of them effectively in the process of communication. In fact, one of the elements in a language ensures the integrity of the language system, while the two are interconnected to the third, and thus all the elements are inextricably linked to each other. Hence, the study of language as a field helps to understand the dialectical relationship between the universe, consciousness, and language on a scientific basis. Field theory also plays an important role in the creation of ideographic dictionaries. Field theory allows language owners to fully understand the basic fund of lexical units used in a particular field, to apply the most essential of them in the communication process.

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